

International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology

(A Peer Reviewed Online Journal)

Impact Factor: 5.164

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**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING SCIENCES & RESEARCH
TECHNOLOGY****A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON SECURITY AND PRIVACY
ARCHITECTURE IN HOME IOT DEVICES****Tolulope Aremu, Oluwatosin Aremu, Samson Arogundade**

School of Information Technology, University of Cincinnati.

Department of Information Technology, University of Bournemouth, United Kingdom.

Manager, IT and Specialized Assurance, Deloitte Nigeria.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14177811

ABSTRACT

The Internet of Things (IoT) has grown more prevalent in residential settings, improving ease and efficiency. However, this integration has raised substantial security and privacy issues, undermining customer confidence. This literature study critically explores the existing security and privacy architecture and trust mechanisms for home IoT devices, demonstrating the breadth of research and potential solutions to these essential challenges.

The study uses a systematic literature review (SLR) technique, using resources from different electronic databases to select and summarize the most relevant papers published between 2013 and 2024. The emphasis is on identifying security and privacy vulnerabilities, analyzing current security frameworks, and unifying the range of solutions targeted at reducing these risks.

Preliminary results show that, despite increased worldwide efforts to develop cybersecurity rules, substantial vulnerabilities exist, such as inadequate authentication mechanisms and insecure communication lines. Progressive solutions for fortifying IoT ecosystems against illegal monitoring and access include hardware-based security, powerful encryption, and the integration of Blockchain and Machine Learning.

This study attempts to traverse the complicated terrain of IoT security and privacy, with the goal of providing clarity on the efficacy of current solutions and identifying areas for further research. It is predicted that the findings will help to enhance strong security and privacy designs, eventually increasing customer confidence in IoT devices.

KEYWORDS: IoT Security, Privacy Architecture, Home IoT Devices, Systematic Literature Review (SLR), Cybersecurity, Authentication Mechanisms, Data Integrity, Confidentiality, Cryptography, Machine Learning for Security, Blockchain Integration, Vulnerability Analysis, Trust Mechanisms, Security Frameworks, Privacy-Enhancing Technologies (PETs), Regulatory Standards, Edge Computing, Fog Computing, Encryption Techniques, Threat Mitigation, Trust and Accountability

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, the Internet of Things (IoT) has emerged in every facet of life, particularly in our complex systems in our homes, Aremu *et al.* (2024). Examples include home-installed gadgets such as smart thermostats and security applications, lighting systems, voice assistants, and others, which radically alter how a person interacts with the internet at home by providing exceptional ease and efficiency. However, such tactics have unexpectedly become a conduit for a wide range of security and privacy issues, causing consumers to lose faith. This literature review focuses on the web of security and privacy architecture, as well as trust mechanisms in home environments for IoT devices, demonstrating both the breadth of research being conducted in that field and the solutions that have been proposed one after the other to address these challenges (Aremu *et al.*, 2024).

The baseline for security in home IoT devices includes more than just access control; it also protects data integrity and confidentiality. Another set of privacy issues is the covert capture, use, and broadcast of personal information, which is exacerbated by always-on and pervasive data-collecting gadgets. When it comes to customer confidence in IoT devices, this is a guarantee of availability, which means that the IoT devices disseminated will be operational enough to supply the services they claim to provide while keeping their security or privacy. When these three parts are considered together, they form a complicated web that this review attempts to navigate.

The importance of tackling these issues cannot be over-emphasized. With reports of IoT devices being hijacked by botnets or spying, the risk of damage is real and multidimensional, impacting not just individual users but also the internet's infrastructure. Furthermore, the intimate nature of the data acquired by home IoT devices—ranging from personal preferences to detailed behavior patterns—raises serious privacy concerns, necessitating the development of strong security and privacy designs.

Despite continued efforts, the diversity of IoT devices, along with their widespread integration into personal areas, creates distinct issues. Aremu *et al.* (2023) states these include the challenge of implementing common security standards, managing devices from numerous manufacturers, and the changing nature of cyber threats. Furthermore, the dynamic nature of the IoT presents issues in establishing confidence, not just in the technologies themselves but also in the organizations who govern and run them.

Several comprehensive literature studies provide incisive assessments and advice for navigating the complicated terrain of privacy and security in IoT devices. Alaba *et al.* (2017) conducts a thorough assessment of IoT security concerns, emphasizing the need of strong cryptographic algorithms and secure communication protocols to guard against a variety of attacks. Similarly, Granjal *et al.* (2015) underline the significance of safeguarding communication channels in IoT networks, arguing that security measures should be included into IoT device design. Sicari *et al.* (2015) concentrate on privacy issues, providing a thorough examination of current privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) and their relevance to IoT situations. Mosenia and Jha (2017) explore the vulnerabilities inherent in IoT devices and propose a multi-layered security method to protect against future attacks. Finally, Lin and Bergmann (2016) investigate the distinct issues of IoT security and privacy, proposing a multidisciplinary strategy that combines technology solutions and legislative frameworks. These assessments highlight the crucial importance of improved security and privacy protections in the developing IoT environment. This literature review aims to disentangle the intricacies of these challenges by combining recent research on security and privacy designs, as well as trust mechanisms in household IoT devices. I hope to answer questions surrounding the level of security of IoT devices against unauthorized surveillance and the measures, policies and security architecture built into IoT devices to prevent spying. My research questions are:

- What is the level of security of common IoT devices against unauthorized surveillance and access?
- What are the measures, policies and security architecture built into IoT devices to prevent spying users?

2. METHODOLOGY

This work introduces a systematic literature review (SLR) technique for investigating current research on security and privacy vulnerabilities in Internet of Things (IoT) devices. The goal of this SLR is to deliberately gather, assess, and combine current research results in order to acquire a thorough knowledge of the security and privacy concerns in the IoT sector.

The research goals are to categorize the various security and privacy issues associated with IoT devices, to critique existing scientific studies addressing IoT security architectures, and to synthesize the discovered solutions, thereby providing a consolidated resource for the broader academic community.

To collect relevant material, an extensive search was undertaken across numerous electronic databases offered by the University of Cincinnati, including the IEEE Xplore digital library, the ACM Digital Library, and the Scopus/Elsevier library. To capture the scope of the issue, search phrases such as "IoT," "IoT devices Security," "Security of IoT home devices", and "security of smart home devices" were carefully selected. The search criteria were configured to include only peer-reviewed journal articles and conference proceedings published in English language between 2013 and 2024.

Articles were chosen based on whether they addressed IoT device security gaps, examined one or more solutions to these security concerns, and were published in respectable academic journals. The study excluded articles that

were not directly relevant to IoT devices, such as those that focused on other sorts of cyber dangers, as well as non-peer-reviewed materials such as lectures and general presentations.

The data extraction method focused on the identified security and privacy issues, suggested remedies, and evaluations of their success. Furthermore, similar themes and patterns were identified, allowing for a synthesis of information that represents the status and direction of IoT security and privacy research.

By concentrating on these areas, the SLR hopes to present a condensed but complete picture of the IoT security and privacy environment, providing insights into current difficulties and prospective solutions. The ultimate objective is to contribute to the continuing conversation in the industry and to help design better secure and privacy preserving IoT ecosystems.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After following through the methodology described in chapter 2, the table below shows some details of the search results obtained.

Table 1: Details of the search results obtained after applying methodology.

Search Query	Library	After filters
Security of IOT home devices	IEEE Xplore	150
Security of IOT home devices	ACM	5433
IoT devices Security	others	

Below are the summaries of the data extracted from the literatures reviewed.

The rapid integration of Internet of Things (IoT) devices into daily life has raised serious security and privacy issues. Sharbaf (2022) emphasizes governments' and enterprises' attempts to set cybersecurity rules to reduce hazards linked with IoT devices. Initiatives such as the Australian government's 13 principles for IoT security and regulations adopted in the United States to boost IoT cybersecurity are part of a worldwide push to promote consumer education and adherence to best practices for a secure digital environment.

Zainuddin et al. (2021) investigate the prevalence of vulnerabilities in IoT ecosystems, identifying prevalent difficulties such as inadequate authentication and unsecured communication. Their paper argues for quick security enhancements by manufacturers, stakeholders, and regulatory authorities, stressing the use of strong authentication mechanisms and frequent security upgrades.

Garcia and Hailu (2021) provide ways for defending against numerous IoT risks, including hardware-based security for device authentication, robust encryption for network security, and sophisticated cryptographic approaches. They emphasize the need of maintaining physical, network, and software security to avoid a variety of assaults.

Alhirabi, Rana, and Perera (2021) investigate the security and privacy needs of IoT, utilizing Continuous Glucose Monitor (CGM) devices to demonstrate the hazards to sensitive data. To mitigate these dangers, they recommend using privacy patterns, lightweight encryption, and privacy-by-design techniques.

Singh, Singh, and Negi (2023) investigate the use of Blockchain, Fog Computing, and Machine Learning (ML) to improve IoT security. Blockchain provides a secure, tamper-proof mechanism for data management that protects data integrity and prevents unwanted access. Fog computing allows for local data processing, reducing the risk of data breaches and improving incident response. ML increases real-time threat detection, such as DoS assaults, as well as authentication via digital fingerprinting.

Gauniyal and Jain (2019) propose for the use of Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) on all IoT devices to improve data security. ECC's complexity makes it a formidable alternative for safeguarding wireless networks in the IoT context.

Sharma, Baghel, and Agarwal (2020) suggest leveraging intelligent visual dashboards, Watson APIs, and new communication protocols like MQTT and CoAP to improve IoT security. They also advise leveraging personal devices, such as cellphones and wearables, for multi-factor authentication.

Sha *et al.* (2017) present EdgeSec, an IoT security service that operates at the Edge layer. EdgeSec attempts to offload complex security chores from IoT devices by combining seven components to build a flexible, comprehensive security architecture that handles IoT security issues.

A survey of 156,680 IoT devices, which included smart TVs, cameras, and printers, discovered that 12.92% were vulnerable. Webcams, particularly D-Link, were most vulnerable, with antiquated protocols offering major dangers. Smart TVs and printers were susceptible to SNMP, emphasizing the need for improved IoT security (Williams *et al.*, 2017).

4. DISCUSSION

The literature examined gives a multifaceted perspective on the present status of IoT security. Sharbat (2022) outlines legislative efforts to protect device security, such as the Australian government's principles and US legislation. Zainuddin *et al.* (2021) identify frequent vulnerabilities and advocate for quick security changes. Garcia and Hailu (2021) present hardware-based and cryptographic methods, whilst Aremu *et al.* (2024) and Alhirabi, Rana, and Perera (2021) address the special privacy requirements of IoT healthcare devices.

Initiatives by governments and businesses are critical for establishing a baseline of security standards. However, as Zainuddin *et al.* (2021) argue, there is an urgent need for manufacturers to implement strict security measures proactively. The broad vulnerabilities pose an obvious and immediate threat to user privacy and data security.

Singh, Singh, and Negi (2023) provide a cutting-edge strategy to preserving IoT ecosystems via the use of Blockchain, Fog Computing, and Machine Learning technology. Gauniyal and Jain (2019) explore the benefits of ECC, a strong encryption standard that is ideally suited to the IoT's specific needs.

According to Williams *et al.* (2017), a considerable number of IoT devices, including smart TVs and cameras, are vulnerable to assaults. This data emphasizes the need for ongoing development in IoT security procedures.

In conclusion, the security of IoT devices is a dynamic topic that needs ongoing awareness and creativity. The literature reviewed emphasizes the need for a holistic solution that involves government regulation, manufacturer accountability, and the use of modern technology.

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